

EDUCATION OF CHILDREN IN NEED IN KOKAN

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ABSTRACT

The vast majority of children in specialized schools in Uzbekistan are often placed there for minor issues like skipping school or leaving home without permission, according to a rapid assessment conducted by UNICEF in cooperation with the Prosecutor General's Office. It aimed to learn about the living conditions, care and services provided for girls in Kokand and Chinaz, and boys in Samarkand and Bakht cities. Results and recommendations of the assessment will help to take further steps towards reorganizing these institutions and reintegrating children placed there into families and society.

The study purpose : Although the specialized institutions have been mandated to support the education and upbringing of children with difficult behaviors, the study reveals that rehabilitation services should be improved and the curricula of the institutions is not adapted to cater to the developmental delays caused by the schooling the children have missed.

"The existing system of crime prevention is based more on identification, rather than changing, correction and rehabilitation," said Svetlana Ryjikova, an international child protection expert working with UNICEF in Uzbekistan. She added that "support services and stronger mechanisms should be available to prevent the placement of children in any institutions, including specialized educational correctional institutions."

"In many cases, the behavior of young people who do not meet the social norms can be related to how they have been brought up," Ms. Ryjikova stressed. "However, labeling a young person "offender" can confine him or her to a particular role, negatively affecting their emotional health and relationships in the future."

Main part:

On 29 May 2019, President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a resolution which envisions the closure of two of the existing four specialized correctional schools for younger pupils and will radically restructure the activities of the remaining two. Further activities for reorganization of the four specialized schools require detailed assessments of the situation of each child using social work tools and supporting families to help reintegrate children.

UNICEF committed to providing help to reorganize the specialized institutions as well as enhancing the capacities of service-providers responsible for supporting children coming out of these facilities. In the 28th school of Uchkuprik district, a "Minister's lesson" was organized

for 9th grade students. Students' knowledge of mathematics, history and chemistry was tested in the lesson. The 3 most active students were given a tablet and a set of books for the class. The young talent Mukhlisahon was presented with a tablet and books and recommended to publish his poems in national newspapers and magazines.

Summary: Kokand, it was noted that teachers are involved in the fate of the country, it is necessary to responsibly provide students with thorough education, improve the socio-spiritual environment at school, increase students' interest in learning. The city's public education department was tasked with creating a healthy environment at the school as soon as possible and recommending a suitable candidate for the school principal.

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